

Determinants of Stock Prices in the LQ45 Index: A Perspective of Capital Structure, Profitability, and Market Performance

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 26 February 2026	This study aims to examine the effect of Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), Return on Assets (ROA), and Earnings per Share (EPS) on the stock prices of companies included in the LQ45 index during the 2020–2024 period. The sampling method employed is purposive sampling, using secondary data obtained from the companies' annual financial statements. This study uses 19 companies as the research sample. Data analysis is conducted using multiple linear regression. The results indicate that the Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) has a negative effect on stock prices, Return on Assets (ROA) has no effect on stock prices, while Earnings per Share (EPS) has a positive effect on stock prices.
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KEYWORDS: Debt to Equity Ratio, Return on Assets, Earnings per Share, Stock Price	

INTRODUCTION

Economic growth in Indonesia has also driven an increase in capital market activities. The existence of the capital market plays an important role as a source of funding for companies as well as a means of investment for the public. The capital market is an organized marketplace where various securities are traded through the stock exchange (Rorizki et al., 2022). It serves as a platform for investors to conduct long-term capital transactions. Therefore, the capital market not only functions as a place for securities transactions but also as an instrument that connects the interests of companies and investors in long-term investment (Supiyanto et al., 2023). Investments made in the capital market not only reflect current conditions but also illustrate investor confidence in a company's future growth and profitability. This function makes the capital market not merely a trading venue but also a mechanism that supports investor capital growth and promotes corporate development through long-term funding. Based on data from the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2024, the average daily transaction value from January to August 2024 reached IDR 11.8 trillion. This figure reflects the high level of trading activity in the capital market and demonstrates its important role as a platform for transactions involving various financial instruments. Assets traded in the capital market generally include securities such as bonds, mutual funds, and stocks (Supiyanto et al., 2023). Shares represent proof of ownership in a company, entitling

shareholders to a portion of the company's income and assets (Herlianto, 2008). Thus, investors who own shares are entitled to a share of profits and company assets in proportion to their ownership. According to the IDX, shares are among the most popular financial market instruments. This indicates that stocks are attractive investment instruments because they provide potential returns as well as ownership rights in a company. Consequently, many investors choose to invest in stocks as a primary form of investment. One of the indicators used by investors before deciding to invest is stock price (Ahmed et al., 2018) Stock prices are formed in the capital market based on supply and demand. In other words, a high stock price indicates increased demand for a company's shares. A company's stock price can reflect investor expectations regarding its performance. Therefore, better financial performance tends to increase demand for the company's shares, which in turn leads to higher stock prices (Cahyono, 2002). In addition to stock prices, investors commonly use stock indices as indicators to evaluate company performance. One of the indices frequently used as a reference is the LQ45 Index. According to Fahri (2015), LQ45 is an index consisting of 45 selected companies that are considered to have high liquidity, accountable performance, and that meet specific criteria determined by the index manager. Therefore, the LQ45 Index provides a clearer picture for investors regarding companies with strong performance and solid fundamentals. Similarly, the Indonesia

Stock Exchange (n.d.) explains that LQ45 reflects the price movements of 45 stocks with high liquidity, large market capitalization, and strong fundamentals. Hence, discussions of the LQ45 Index cannot be separated from stock prices, as the index represents 45 highly liquid companies and serves as a benchmark for overall capital market conditions. However, the high level of trading activity in the capital market also results in stock price fluctuations influenced by various internal and external factors. One significant internal factor is the company's fundamental condition, which can be measured through financial ratios such as Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), Earnings per Share (EPS), and Return on Assets (ROA). These ratios are often used in research to evaluate corporate financial performance and its relationship with stock price movements. Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) is a ratio that compares total debt to total equity of a company. It indicates the extent to which shareholders' equity can cover the company's obligations to creditors (Rudianto, 2021). In other words, it measures how much debt is used in the company's capital structure. Research conducted by Siregar (2020) states that the higher the level of corporate debt, the greater the risk borne by the company. However, if the cost of debt is lower than the cost of equity, the use of debt can increase profitability and ultimately drive stock price growth. Theoretically, high debt levels increase financial risk, which may reduce investor interest and negatively affect stock prices. However, previous research findings show inconsistencies. Adawiyah and Amirudin (2024) found that DER has a negative effect on stock prices, while other studies indicate that DER does not significantly influence stock prices (Yuliana & Santoso, 2025). These differing results suggest empirical inconsistencies, indicating the need for further investigation into the effect of DER on stock prices. Return on Assets (ROA), according to Astuti et al. (2021), is a ratio that measures how effectively a company's assets generate net profit. In other words, ROA indicates the net profit earned for every rupiah invested in total assets. A high ROA serves as an indicator for investors that the company is effectively utilizing its assets to generate profit. An increase in ROA reflects the company's improved ability to generate profits, which has the potential to increase stock prices and shareholder returns (Lubis et al., 2025). Theoretically, a high ROA reflects effective asset utilization and should increase investor interest, thereby positively affecting stock prices. However, previous research findings are inconsistent. Rahman and Elizabeth (2024) found that ROA does not have a significant effect on stock prices, whereas Dewi and Pusparini (2024) found that ROA has a positive effect on stock prices. These conflicting results indicate empirical inconsistencies, suggesting that the influence of ROA on stock prices requires further examination. Earnings per Share (EPS), according to Rudianto (2021), represents the amount of net profit earned by a company for each outstanding share.

In other words, EPS indicates the profit received by shareholders for each share owned. Positive EPS growth is generally viewed as a favourable signal by investors because it demonstrates the company's ability to generate sustainable profits and strengthens investor confidence in long-term investment (Jannah et al., 2024). Theoretically, a high EPS provides a positive signal to investors, as it reflects higher earnings per share and should contribute to rising stock prices. However, previous research findings are also inconsistent. Munggaran et al. (2017) found that EPS has a positive and significant effect on stock prices, whereas Rostini et al. (2024) found that EPS does not significantly affect stock prices. These differences reflect empirical inconsistencies and indicate the need for further research. This study aims to examine the effect of Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), Return on Assets (ROA), and Earnings per Share (EPS) on the stock prices of companies included in the LQ45 Index during the 2020–2024 period.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theory Signal

According to Spence (1973) in his research entitled *Job Market Signaling*, signaling theory explains that the party that owns more information (insider) can give signals to other parties who have less information (outsider), so that decision-making can be done more appropriately. Spence gave an example of this theory through the job market, when applicants show their ability or quality to companies through the level of education they possess. In the capital market context, signaling theory is used to explain how company management gives signals to investors through financial information such as profit reports, financial ratios, as well as dividend policy, which ultimately can influence investment decisions. Signaling theory explains the existence of differences in information between management and investors regarding the company's condition. In this situation, management actions can become signals for investors in evaluating company prospects. One form of signal is reflected through corporate financial decisions, such as the use of debt or profit distribution. When a company shows good financial performance, that can become a positive signal for investors that the company has good prospects in the future. On the other hand, negative signals appear when financial indicators show a decline in performance, which can lower investor confidence and impact stock prices (Brigham & Houston, 2019). Based on signaling theory, differences in information between management and investors make every corporate financial decision a form of indirect communication to the market. Through financial ratios, management can give signals to investors about the company's condition and prospects. Positive signals usually increase investor confidence and interest, while negative signals can lower evaluations of companies and impact stock prices.

Stock price

Stock price is the current value of cash flows that will be received by shareholders in the future. Thus, stock price reflects investor expectations regarding a company's ability to generate future benefits (Zaimsyah et al., 2019). Meanwhile, according to Brigham & Houston (2019), stock price is the actual market price of a share that can be directly observed in publicly traded companies. This means that stock price is formed based on the interaction between demand and supply in the market. From both understandings, it can be concluded that stock price not only reflects current market conditions but also reflects investor assessments of the company's fundamental development and performance. An increase in stock price can occur due to various factors such as positive economic growth, good company performance, as well as supportive market sentiment. When company performance improves, stock price also tends to rise because investors assess the company's prospects as better (Harahap, 2024). On the other hand, a decline in company performance can reduce investor confidence and cause stock prices to weaken. Thus, stock prices tend to fluctuate following changes in company performance and conditions.

Debt to Equity Ratio

Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) is a ratio used to see how much a company uses loan funds compared to its own capital in operating its business activities. It describes the extent to which the company's capital is capable of bearing all of its obligations. In line with this, according to Putri et al. (2022), DER is the comparison between total debt and total equity owned by a company (Ratih et al., 2013). The DER value shows a number less than one if the proportion of debt used to finance the company's assets is smaller compared to equity. On the other hand, if the DER value is higher than one, then the company uses more debt than its own capital. This condition describes the extent to which the company depends on external financing to operate its activities (Rudianto, 2021). Good financial performance can also become an attraction for potential investors. Companies that are able to show good performance will increase investor interest in buying their shares because they are considered to have promising profit prospects. Thus, when demand for shares increases, the company's stock price tends to increase as well (Siregar, 2020).

Return on Asset

Return on Assets (ROA) is a financial ratio used to evaluate the extent to which a company is able to generate net profit from the total assets it owns. ROA measures a company's overall ability to generate profit relative to its total assets. This ratio describes the effectiveness of a company in utilizing its assets to obtain profits (Rostini et al., 2024; Sukron et al., 2025). A high ROA level reflects good company performance, while a low ROA can occur as a

consequence of high debt usage that reduces the company's net profit. This shows that ROA becomes an important indicator in evaluating the efficiency of asset utilization in generating profit, which in the end can influence investor perception and stock price movements in the market (Brigham & Houston, 2019).

Earnings per Share

Earnings per Share (EPS) is a ratio that shows the amount of profit earned by a company for each share owned by shareholders. EPS describes the level of net profit generated by the company for each share during its operating activities. Thus, EPS reflects the company's ability to generate profit for shareholders through each share owned (Fahri, 2015; Tambuwun et al., 2024). An increase in EPS reflects an improvement in company performance because it shows the growth of profit generated per share over time. Thus, EPS becomes one of the important indicators for investors in evaluating a company's prospects. The higher the EPS value, the greater the potential increase in stock price because it reflects the company's ability to provide profit for shareholders (Brigham & Houston, 2019).

Influence of Debt to Equity Ratio on Stock Prices

Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) is a ratio used to evaluate the comparison between total debt and total equity. This ratio is useful to determine how much of the company's funds originate from creditors compared to its own capital. In other words, DER shows every rupiah of equity used as collateral against the company's debts (Kasmir, 2020). A low DER value reflects the company's ability to pay off its obligations efficiently (Maharani & Kurnia, 2024). On the other hand, a high DER value can cause concern for investors because it shows the company's high dependence on debt in its operating activities. Previous research conducted by Siregar (2020) shows that there is a negative and significant influence between Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) and stock price. Investors generally evaluate that the larger the portion of company funding originating from debt compared to equity, the higher the company's risk. This risk will indirectly be borne by investors. Therefore, through DER, management can give signals to investors regarding the company's condition and prospects. Thus, a negative signal from DER can result in a decline in stock price. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is formulated: H1: Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) has a negative effect on stock prices of companies included in the LQ45 Index for the 2020–2024 period.

Influence of Return on Asset on Stock Prices

Return on Assets (ROA) is a ratio used to measure a company's ability to generate profit from its assets (Sukmawati & Grasela, 2016). ROA also serves as an indicator of the extent to which a company is able to utilize its financial resources to create value for shareholders. A higher ROA value indicates that the company is more

efficient in managing all of its resources to generate profit. This signifies good financial performance and can increase investor confidence in the company’s prospects (Hery, 2014). Previous research conducted by Permatasari and Suraya (2025) shows that Return on Assets (ROA) has a positive and significant effect on stock price. Companies that are able to manage their assets efficiently can generate maximum profit. A high ROA value indicates good company performance and efficiency in asset utilization. This condition provides a positive signal to investors regarding the company’s ability to generate profit. Thus, a positive signal from ROA can drive an increase in stock price.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is formulated: H2: Return on Assets (ROA) has a positive effect on stock prices of companies included in the LQ45 Index for the 2020–2024 period.

Influence Earnings per Share On Stock Prices

Earnings per Share (EPS) is the result of dividing the company’s net profit by the number of outstanding shares. This ratio describes the amount of profit earned by the company for each share owned by investors (Kumar, 2017). The higher the EPS value, the more it gives a positive signal to shareholders because it shows the greater profit provided by the company to its shareholders (Adriani & Nurjihan, 2020). Previous research conducted by Nur et al. (2025) showed that Earnings per Share (EPS) has a positive and significant effect on stock price. The greater the net profit generated by the company compared to the number of outstanding shares, the higher the resulting EPS value. This condition becomes a positive signal for investors because it shows the company’s ability to provide profit for shareholders. Therefore, EPS can give a positive signal to investors regarding the level of profit earned per share. A positive signal from EPS can increase investor interest, thereby impacting the increase in stock price. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is formulated H3: Earnings per Share (EPS) has a positive effect on stock prices of companies included in the LQ45 Index for the 2020–2024 period.

Framework Study The framework of thinking in this study is depicted through a chart as follows:

Figure 1 Research Framework

RESEARCH METHODS

Sample Population

The population in this study consists of all companies included in the LQ45 Index on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2020–2024 period. The selection of the five-year period was conducted because the researchers wanted to provide updated research results using more recent data. The sampling technique used is purposive sampling, which is a method of selecting samples based on certain criteria. The criteria used in this study are companies that were consistently listed in the LQ45 Index during the 2020–2024 period, companies that issued complete annual financial statements, presented in rupiah during the research period, and audited by independent auditors.

Method Data collection

In this study, the data are collected through documentation study and literature study. The documentation study is conducted by collecting secondary data in the form of companies’ annual reports obtained from the Indonesia Stock Exchange website (www.idx.co.id) and the companies’ official websites. Meanwhile, the literature study is sourced from scientific journals, articles, books, and previous research findings.

Definition and Measurement of Research Variables

The dependent variable in this study is stock price. Stock price is the value of a share formed through the buying and selling transaction mechanism in the capital market. Stock price reflects the value of companies traded in the capital market and can change following the dynamics of demand and supply from market participants (Jogiyanto, 2016). Stock price is measured using the closing price of companies included in the LQ45 Index during the 2020–2024 period. Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) describes the proportion between total debt and total equity owned by a company. This ratio shows the extent to which equity is able to cover all of the company’s obligations. The higher the DER value, the greater the risk faced by the company because its dependence on debt also increases (Siswanto, 2021). DER can be calculated by comparing total debt to total equity of the company, with the following formula (Kasmir, 2020):

$$DER = \frac{\text{Total Debt}}{\text{Total Equity}} \times 100\%$$

- H1 Return on Assets (ROA) describes a company’s ability to generate profit from the total assets it owns. This ratio is one of the important indicators used to evaluate how efficiently a
- H2 company utilizes its assets to obtain profit. The higher the ROA value, the greater the net profit generated, indicating
- H3 that the company is able to manage its assets optimally. On the other hand, a low or even negative ROA value indicates that the company has not been efficient in utilizing its assets to generate profit, and this can be a sign of potential losses (Practical et al., 2024). ROA can be calculated using the following formula (Ramadan & Nursito, 2021):

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$$ROA = \frac{\text{Net profit after tax}}{\text{Total Asset}} \times 100\%$$

Earnings per Share (EPS) is a profitability ratio that reflects the amount of net profit earned by a company for each outstanding share. This ratio shows how much income will be received by investors for each share they own. The higher the EPS value, the greater the profit received by shareholders, which indicates better company performance. On the other hand, if the EPS value is low, the profit obtained by investors also decreases, which can influence investment interest (Darmadji & Fakhruddin, 2011). EPS can be calculated using the following formula (Ratih et al., 2013):

$$EPS = \frac{\text{Net profit after tax}}{\text{Number of ordinary shares issued}}$$

Method Analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis is used to describe or analyse the data for each variable used in the research (Juliandi et al., 2014). This analysis includes measures such as the average value (mean), minimum value (min), maximum value (max), standard deviation, and the number of observations of the data used. Data analysis uses a multiple linear regression model by performing a t-test. Classical assumption tests are conducted to confirm that the regression model fulfils the basic assumptions so that the estimated results obtained are BLUE (Best Linear Unbiased Estimator). The classical assumption tests in this study include the normality test, multicollinearity test, autocorrelation test, and heteroscedasticity test. In addition to the classical assumption tests, an F-test and a coefficient of determination test (R²) are also conducted. Multiple linear regression analysis is used to test the hypotheses that have been formulated previously, with the general equation as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon$$

Y = Stock price

X1 = Debt to Equity

X2 = Return on Asset

X3 = Earnings per Share

A = Constant

β1, β2, β3, β4, β5 = Coefficient values regression

ε = Standard error

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the sample selection, as shown in Table 1, indicate that 19 companies were obtained in accordance with the predetermined criteria, with a total of 95 observations analyzed. The results of the descriptive statistical analysis are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Sample Criteria

No	Criteria Sample	Amount
1.	Companies included in the LQ45 Index on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2020–2024 period	24
2.	Companies that do not publish complete annual financial reports, are not presented in rupiah, or are not audited	(5)
Number of Sample Companies		19
Number of Observations (19 companies × 5 years)		95

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Research Variables

Statistics Descriptive					
	Frequency	Minimum Value	Maximum Value	Flat-Flat	Standard Deviation
DER	95	0.170	16,079	2,805	3,392
ROA	95	0.004	0.349	0.076	0.071
EPS	95	34,709	6,164,300	594,521	1,040,254
Stock price	95	655	26,775	6,113,950	5,400,116

The normality test results in Table 3, using the One-Sample Kolmogorov–Smirnov Test, show that the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value is 0.200, which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that the research data are normally distributed.

The results of the multicollinearity test in Table 4 show that all independent variables have tolerance values above 0.10 and VIF values below 10. This indicates that no multicollinearity problem occurs. Based on the heteroscedasticity test results in Table 5, using the Park Test, the ROA, DER, and EPS variables have significance values of 0.349, 0.074, and 0.719, respectively, all of which are greater than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that the regression model does not experience heteroscedasticity.

Based on the results of the Durbin–Watson test in Table 6, the DW (d) value obtained is 2.069. With the number of observations N = 95 and the number of independent variables k = 3, the values obtained are dL = 1.602, dU = 1.732, and 4 – dU = 2.269. The test results show that dU < d < 4 – dU, or 1.732 < 2.069 < 2.269, so it can be concluded that the null hypothesis is accepted, which means there is no autocorrelation in the regression model.

Table 3. Normality Test Results One- Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Sample Test			
		Unstandardized Residual	
Extreme differences	Absolute	0.065	
	Positive	0.049	
	Negative	-0.065	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.200	
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed)	Sig	0.392	
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bond	0.379
		Upper Bond	0.404

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Results

Multicollinearity Test		
Collinearity Statistics		
Model	Tolerance	VIF
DER	0.873	1,145
ROA	0.888	1,127
EPS	0.979	1,021

Table 5. Results of Heteroscedasticity Test (Park Test)

Park Test Heteroscedasticity Test	
Variables	Sig.
DER	0.349
ROA	0.074
EPS	0.719

Table 1 Autocorrelation Test Results Durbin-Watson

Frequency	Durbin-Watson
95	2,069

The results of the multiple linear regression test to determine the effect of the independent variables, namely Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), Return on Assets (ROA), and Earnings per Share (EPS), on Stock Price are presented in Table 7.

Table 2 Multiple Linear Regression Results

Variables	Coefficient Regression (β)	T	Sig.	Information
(Constant)	5,420	17,440	0.001	
DER	-0.045	-2,699	0.008	H1 is supported

ROA	-1,112	-1,390	0.168	H2 is not supported
EPS	0.557	11,076	0.001	Sig. F = 0.001
R = 0.778				
R Square = 0.606				
Adj R Square = 0.593				

The result of the regression equation is as follow:

$$Y = 5.42 - 0.045DER - 1.112ROA + 0.557EPS + \epsilon$$

The Adjusted R Square test results (Adj. R²), based on Table 7, show that the R² value is 0.606. This indicates that variables X1, X2, and X3 simultaneously explain 60.6% of variable Y, while the remaining 39.4% is influenced by other variables outside the research model. The F-test results, with a significance level of 0.05 (5%), show that the significance value of the influence of variables X1 Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), X2 Return on Assets (ROA), and X3 Earnings per Share (EPS) on Stock Price (Y) is 0.001. The significance value is smaller than the 0.05 significance level; therefore, it can be concluded that the regression model is appropriate and can be used to explain the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

Influence of Debt to Equity (DER) on Stock Price

The research results show that Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) has a negative and significant effect on stock price. This is indicated by the DER regression coefficient value of -0.045 with a p-value of 0.008, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. Thus, the first hypothesis stating that Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) has a negative effect on stock prices of companies included in the LQ45 Index for the 2020–2024 period is supported. A high debt ratio reflects an increasing burden of obligations to external parties, which ultimately increases the company’s financial risk. This condition can reduce investor confidence and consequently impact the decline in stock price. These research results are in line with signaling theory proposed by Spence (1973), where published company information, in this case DER, becomes a signal for investors in making investment decisions. A high DER reflected in financial reports provides a negative signal to investors, thereby influencing investment decisions and impacting the decline in stock price.

In addition, the results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Ratih et al. (2013), which stated that DER has a negative effect on stock price. However, these results are not consistent with the findings of Sinaga et al. (2023), who found that DER has a positive effect on stock price.

Influence of Return on Assets (ROA) on Stock Price

The research results show that Return on Assets (ROA) does not have a significant effect on stock price. This is evidenced by a p-value of 0.168, which is greater than the significance

level of 0.05. Thus, ROA is stated to have no significant effect on stock price, and the second hypothesis stating that Return on Assets (ROA) has a positive effect on stock prices of companies included in the LQ45 Index for the 2020–2024 period is not supported. The results indicate that a company’s ability to generate profit through the utilization of its assets has not become the main consideration for investors in making investment decisions. Companies with high or low ROA values do not necessarily reflect the company’s overall condition. Investors tend to pay more attention to indicators that directly reflect economic benefits for shareholders, such as Earnings per Share (EPS), because it is considered to better represent actual profit per share. Therefore, ROA may not directly impact stock price movements. These research results are not fully in line with signaling theory proposed by Spence (1973). ROA may not be considered a primary factor in investment decision-making in the capital market, but it can still be used as additional information for investors. This study is consistent with research conducted by Rumiatiingsih et al. (2021), which states that ROA does not significantly affect stock price. However, the results of this study are not consistent with research by Agustina et al. (2024), who found that Return on Assets (ROA) has a positive and significant effect on stock price.

Influence of Earnings per Share (EPS) on Stock Price

The third hypothesis, which states that Earnings per Share (EPS) has a positive effect on stock prices of companies included in the LQ45 Index for the 2020–2024 period, is supported. This is proven by the regression estimation results, which show that the EPS variable (X3) has a positive regression coefficient of 0.557 with a p-value of 0.001, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. EPS reflects a company’s ability to generate earnings per share; therefore, the higher the EPS, the greater the level of profit received by investors. This condition makes the company’s shares more attractive in the eyes of investors. Investors tend to use EPS as one of the main indicators in evaluating company performance and prospects because the information is easily obtained, easy to understand, and directly describes the company’s level of profitability. These research results are in line with signaling theory proposed by Spence (1973), which published financial information, including EPS, functions as a signal for investors in making investment decisions. A high EPS provides a positive signal about company performance, which can increase demand for shares and ultimately raise stock prices. Thus, the results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Astuti and Setiawati (2024), which states that EPS has a positive and significant effect on stock price. However, the results of this study are not consistent with research by Salim et al. (2025), who found that partially EPS has a negative effect on stock price.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results regarding the influence of Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), Return on Assets (ROA), and Earnings per Share (EPS) on stock prices of companies listed in the LQ45 Index for the 2020–2024 period, it can be concluded that Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) has a negative effect on stock prices, Return on Assets (ROA) has no significant effect on stock prices, and Earnings per Share (EPS) has a positive effect on stock prices. The findings indicate that a high Debt to Equity Ratio sends a negative signal to investors because it reflects a higher level of financial risk within the company. Conversely, a high Earnings per Share provides a positive signal, as it reflects the company’s ability to generate profit per share, thereby increasing investor interest and encouraging an increase in stock prices. Meanwhile, Return on Assets has not become a primary indicator used by investors to evaluate stock price movements of companies included in the LQ45 Index during the research period. This study has several limitations that may have influenced the research results. First, the composition of companies in the LQ45 Index is not consistent over time, as changes in the list of issuers occur periodically. This condition limits the number of companies that meet the research criteria and does not cover all companies that have ever been included in the index. Second, the research period coincided with the COVID-19 pandemic, which caused various economic shocks affecting companies’ financial performance. This situation may have influenced the testing results of the variables examined in this study. Based on the research findings and identified limitations, several suggestions can be proposed for future researchers who intend to examine similar topics or variables. Future studies are expected to consider the existence of stock split policies, particularly in the banking sector, so that appropriate data adjustments can be made to ensure comparability of stock values before and after stock splits. Additionally, to increase the number of observations, future researchers may expand the sample criteria, for example, by not limiting financial reports only to companies using the rupiah currency, as long as the data can still be consistently adjusted and compared.

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